

PRACTICE-ORIENTED PROFESSIONAL SELECTION, AS ONE OF THE GUARANTORS OF RAISING THE LEVEL OF EDUCATION IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS OF POWER STRUCTURES OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Introduction. At the present stage of development of the state, well-organized selection of candidates, preparation and development of the educational environment to provide highly qualified specialists in all spheres of life of the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the priority tasks. After all, our youth is our future, and our future certainly depends on how well we carry out training, selection and create conditions for the development of the abilities of our youth. However, in order to achieve development, first of all, it is necessary to take care of the security of our independent and sovereign Uzbekistan.

ABSTRACT

This article examines the main problematic issues of professional selection of candidates for higher educational institutions of power structures as one of the main components in giving a modern look to the professional Armed Forces of the state. The analysis of psychological and methodological research on this topic is made. The necessity of developing methods of drawing up (psychological passports) of specialties, competence profiles of specialists (military profессиography) has been substantiated.

The function of ensuring security is entrusted to the Armed Forces (AF) of the Republic of Uzbekistan (RU), which are in constant readiness to repel any kind of aggression.

To date, all power structures of the Armed Forces are striving to increase the level of professionalism in its ranks, to provide modern weapons and military equipment with a very complex software component, which requires highly qualified specialists in various fields of military affairs. It is a high-quality professional selection, based on the availability of demanded personality traits,

knowledge and skills, with the dynamic development of the educational environment in higher military educational institutions (HMEI), will ensure the needs of the Armed Forces of Uzbekistan for highly qualified specialists at a qualitatively new level.

The relevance of this issue lies in considering the features of the work of military psychologists with candidates for admission to the Higher Educational Institution of Higher Education, in the selection of candidates for the chosen specialty. At the stage of professional selection, the priority is to determine the list of psychological and physiological criteria demanded for the specifics of performing the tasks assigned based on the specific profile of a given specialist in the predicted unit.

The purpose of the study was to improve the system of professional selection of candidates in specialties in the Higher Educational Institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in order to fulfill the tasks set by the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 3, 2019 No. PP-4306 "On measures to organize a continuous system for identifying gifted youth and training highly qualified personnel." Research methods.

To achieve this goal, the following research methods were used:

- theoretical analysis of psychological, pedagogical, military and methodological literature on the organization of the system of professional selection of candidates for higher educational institutions;

The scientific and practical significance of the article is as follows:

in defining it as one of the most important conditions for the training of highly

qualified officers based on modern requirements for a professional army; in the high-quality conduct of the professional selection of candidates for the HMEI, and the training of specialists in various fields of military affairs;

identification of professionally significant psychological characteristics of specialists that determine the success of professional activities in predictable positions in the units of the security forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

determination of the essence of professional suitability, especially important qualities and psychological characteristics of specialists at the stage of selection and quality control of their physical and psychological readiness to perform service and combat missions;

highlighting and characterizing the professionally important values of the specialist candidate, which are the main component of the system of professional competencies, including:

- instrumental values (means of realizing professional activity) based on the nervous system and characteristics of the candidate's temperament;

- terminal values (values-goals of professional activity)

based on the moral and ethical standards of the candidate;

determination of tasks and principles for the implementation of professional selection of candidates for admission to the Higher Educational Institutions of Higher Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, at the sitting of the Security Council on 10.01.2018, noted the following: "The heads of power ministries and departments should develop fundamentally new documents on the

organization of physical and psychological and psychological stress”.

The problem of training military personnel has always been and remains the subject of close public attention. The officer acts as a leader in the performance of service-combat and educational tasks, as a teacher and educator, organizer and performer of cultural and leisure work and everyday life of all military personnel subordinate to him. For the high-quality performance of these types of activities, an officer must be a comprehensively and harmoniously developed personality. Therefore, at all levels and in all spheres of military education, an active search for ways is underway:

a) improving the quality of military professional training;

b) updating and deepening its content, adequate to transformations in the socio-economic and military spheres.

However, despite the significant attention of psychological and pedagogical science to issues of selection and training of military personnel, HMEI graduates still do not fully meet the requirements of the present time. This is evidenced by the high turnover of military personnel and the ongoing process of

their "aging", the presence of a significant number of vacancies, due to insufficient number of highly qualified specialists in technical, rear engineering and other specialties.

Today, the general professional selection of candidates

for suitability for training in the HMEI, is carried out by a separate approved by order (order) of the head of the HMEI commission with a mandatory medical examination, which includes psychologists who carry out their activities.

The professional selection of candidates for each specialty separately is carried out by the personnel apparatus of the HMEI under the direct control of the relevant ministry (department), and this work is carried out with the verification of exclusively the intellectual abilities of the candidate by testing method, or by a written examination.

Identification of professionally significant psychological characteristics, instrumental values, for each specialty separately, based directly on the nature of the specialty chosen by the candidate

and determining the success of professional activity in the predicted positions in the units of the power structures of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the course of professional selection is not carried out. This selection is not carried out due to the lack of scientifically grounded, practically tested methods of professional selection of qualities and characteristics for each specialty

separately based on the specifics and type of activity. The lack of these methods of selection of candidates leads to the fact that cadets are admitted to the Higher Educational Institution of Higher Education without taking into account the psychological predisposition to the chosen specialty, which in the process of further training greatly complicates the process of developing the abilities, skills and abilities characteristic of the specialty.

In this connection, it becomes obvious that an increase in the effectiveness of training in the HMEI can be achieved only when the correspondence of the requirements of the activity, psychological and personal qualities and characteristics of candidates is ensured to the maximum extent. In other words, a soldier must have a sufficient

psychological resource to carry out specific military activities in the chosen specialty. In the interests of ensuring such compliance, it is advisable to consider the highlighted general logic of professional psychological selection in the Armed

Forces of the Russian Federation (RF), including forces, means, a system of scientific and methodological support for professional psychological selection (Рис.№ 1).

Analysis of military threats, scientific assessment of trends in the art of war, forecasting the nature of wars and local military conflicts, determining the "professional" image of the future Armed Forces of the Russian Federation

Studying the requirements of military specialties and certain types of military activity for the mental qualities of military personnel - potential subjects of this activity and drawing up a psychological classification of military positions

Development of profессиograms and psychograms (psychological passports) of specialties, competence profiles of specialists (military profессиography)

Study of trends in the labor market, the demographic situation in the country. Informing citizens about vacant military specialties and the requirements and requirements for the individual psychological and personal qualities of their potential subjects (professional and psychological orientation of citizens)

Study of the level of conformity (suitability) of the individual psychological and personal qualities of candidates to the requirements of any of the military specialties (potbor) or a specific military specialty, activity (selection) (professional psychological selection)

Distribution of servicemen by military specialties, types of activities, units, positions

Professional and psychological support of military activities of a serviceman

Rice. № 1. The system of training and professional psychological selection in the RF Armed Forces.

One of the objective factors of the above situation in the selection of candidates for the Higher Educational Institution of Higher Education is the extremely pronounced lack of scientific research in

the field of military psychology in the Republic of Uzbekistan. This was apparently due to the fact that, in the former Soviet period, the center was not interested in the development of military psychology in the union republics. In addition, psychodiagnostics was one of the neglected areas in Soviet psychology.

These are the distant consequences of the development of certain types of psychology in the Soviet period, especially a sharp lag in the practical application of valuable theoretical propositions. According to the theory, Soviet science not only did not yield, and often even outstripped the achievements of scientists in developed countries, but was severely "lame" in implementation and effective use in practice. Sometimes ideology also negatively influenced the scientific and practical development of topical problems of science.

A prominent Russian psychologist E.A. Klimov formulated the "golden rule" of labor psychology and, at the same time, the central problem of human studies areas of knowledge serving the solution of this problem, consisting in establishing the best mutual correspondence (reciprocity) of a person as a subject of labor, on the one hand, and objective requirements of a socially fixed job post - on the other.

The problem of the correspondence between the personality and the specialty can be adequately solved only if the whole complex of requirements is taken into account: the requirements of the individual to the activity and, conversely, the requirements of the professional activity to the individual. The implementation of this approach in practice is an important condition and prerequisite for improving the entire system of professional training of highly qualified military specialists.

The professional suitability of a person for a certain specialty is a combination of special knowledge, skills and abilities that determine a person's ability to perform a certain professional activity by specialization, determined as professional preparedness,

and the emotional-evaluative attitude of the individual to the work performed and the conditions of its course (emotional sphere of activity), called job satisfaction.

Based on the foregoing, a serviceman can be considered professionally fit if he successfully masters and implements the duties assigned to him related to professional activity, positively evaluates his activities in the chosen specialty and is satisfied with the process and results of this activity.

According to the famous Soviet psychologist N.D. Levitova, becomes relevant:

- in the selection and selection of personnel (determining the suitability of a candidate for a given specialty);
- when choosing a profession, determining what specialty a person is most suitable for;
- when training in a specialty (the formation of a person's suitability for a particular job).

Conclusion. Agreeing with the aspects reflected in the article, we note the need for further work on the development of separate methods for professional selection for each specialty separately. Based on the physical and psychological characteristics of the specialist's activity, the characteristics of the nervous system and the temperament of the candidate, and not only from the results of his general test for suitability for admission to the Higher Educational Institution. Developing a list of specific professional competencies of a serviceman for each specialty personally.

Thus, the improvement of the system of professional selection in HEU, which is one of the important aspects of increasing the professionalism of officers in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan and

improving military education, serves as the basis for drawing the following **conclusions:**

1. It is necessary to methodically substantiate the list of qualities necessary for a candidate at the stage of professional selection, for specific groups of similar specialties in the Higher Educational Institutions and divisions of the power structures of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
2. It is expedient to define military-professional orientation on mastering a certain military specialty from candidates for training in HEI in the selection of candidates in specialized secondary specialized profile

and general educational institutions of secondary education;

3. The most acute problem of selection is for those military specialties and positions where a minor mistake related to the mental characteristics of a soldier can lead to serious consequences for the loss of human resources, for example: a sapper, air traffic controller, operator, reconnaissance officer, commander, etc.
4. Determine a set of measures aimed at professional and psychological support of cadets in the course of the educational process, and predicting their success in future officer positions in the power structures of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

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